

Evaluation of Cognitive Load While Performing Code Comprehension Tasks – Code Comprehension Questions

Start of Block: Small Code 1

Small Code: DiscountCalc

End of Block: Small Code 1

Start of Block: Small Code 1 Comprehension

There is a potential logical issue in how discounts are combined. Which statement is true?

- A) The fixed \$5 member discount is applied BEFORE the 10% quantity discount
 - B) The fixed \$5 member discount is applied AFTER the 10% quantity discount
 - C) The member discount overwrites the quantity discount
 - D) If the price is 0, the result becomes -5.0
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How is the 'total' price determined if quantity is 100?

- A) It is the raw price * quantity
 - B) It is (price * quantity) reduced by 10%
 - C) It is always 0
 - D) It is (price * quantity) - 5
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What is the result of calculatePrice(10.0, 15, false)? (Result 2)

- A) 150.0
 - B) 145.0
 - C) 135.0
 - D) 130.0
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What is the scope of the 'total' variable?

- A) It is a class-level field
 - B) It is a global variable
 - C) It is local to the calculatePrice method
 - D) It is passed as a parameter
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End of Block: Small Code 1 Comprehension

Start of Block: Small Code 2

Small Code: Course

End of Block: Small Code 2

Start of Block: Small Code 2 Comprehension

What happens if the course code is "CS3XYZ" (ending in non-digits)?

- A) isUpperLevel returns true
 - B) isUpperLevel returns false
 - C) isUpperLevel throws a NumberFormatException
 - D) isUpperLevel throws an IndexOutOfBoundsException
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What criteria defines an "Upper Level" course in this code?

- A) Credits must be strictly greater than 3
 - B) The course code must end with a number ≥ 300
 - C) The title must contain "Advanced"
 - D) The code length must be exactly 5
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What is the console output of statement 1: `c1.isUpperLevel()`? (Code: "CS214")

- A) true
 - B) false
 - C) null
 - D) Error
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The logic in `isUpperLevel` primarily relies on parsing which field of the Course class?

- A) title
- B) credits
- C) code
- D) None, it only uses local variables

End of Block: Small Code 2 Comprehension

Start of Block: Medium Code 1

Medium Code: EmployeeDirectory

End of Block: Medium Code 1

Start of Block: Med Code 1 Comprehension

What happens if you try to add an employee with an ID that already exists?

- A) The existing name is overwritten
 - B) An exception is thrown
 - C) The method returns false and the map is unchanged
 - D) A duplicate entry is created
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Which option best describes the printDirectory method?

- A) It prints names sorted by ID
- B) It iterates through all keys and prints the ID and associated Name
- C) It removes all employees while printing
- D) It prints only the first 10 employees

What is the return value of r2 (dir.addEmployee("E001", "Bob")) in the main method?

- A) true
 - B) false
 - C) null
 - D) "Alice"
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The 'employees' field is defined as `Map`. What specific implementation is used in the constructor?

- A) TreeMap
- B) ArrayList
- C) HashMap
- D) LinkedList

End of Block: Med Code 1 Comprehension

Start of Block: Medium Code 2

Medium Code: Inventory

End of Block: Medium Code 2

Start of Block: Med Code 2 Comprehension

In 'findMostExpensive', what happens if two items have the exact same highest price?

- A) The method returns the one added most recently
 - B) The method returns the one encountered first in the list
 - C) The method throws an exception
 - D) The method returns both names
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What logic does 'addItem' enforce before adding to the list?

- A) Name must not be null/empty, and price must be non-negative
 - B) Name must be unique
 - C) Price must be greater than 0
 - D) List size must be less than 10
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How many items end up in the list after the main execution (inv.items.size())?

- A) 2
 - B) 3
 - C) 4
 - D) 1
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'Item' is defined as a 'private static class'. What does this mean for its accessibility?

- A) It can be accessed by any other class in the project
- B) It can only be used within the Inventory class
- C) It cannot have any fields
- D) It cannot be instantiated

End of Block: Med Code 2 Comprehension

Start of Block: Large Code 1

Large Code: HotelBooking

End of Block: Large Code 1

Start of Block: Large Code 1 Comprehension

If checkIn is called when all rooms are already occupied, what happens?

- A) The application crashes
 - B) It overwrites the first room
 - C) It returns false and prints a message
 - D) It automatically creates a new room
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How does the constructor initialize the room numbers?

- A) Starting from 0 sequentially
- B) Starting from 101 (100 + i) sequentially
- C) Randomly
- D) All rooms are room 100

Which room number is assigned to "Charlie" in the main method?

- A) 101
 - B) 102
 - C) 103
 - D) None
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The 'rooms' list stores objects of which type?

- A) String
- B) Integer
- C) Room (inner class)
- D) Object

End of Block: Large Code 1 Comprehension

Start of Block: Large Code 2

Large Code: TicTacToe

End of Block: Large Code 2

Start of Block: Large Code 2 Comprehension

If a player tries to place a mark on an already occupied spot, what happens to the turn?

- A) The turn passes to the next player
 - B) The turn remains with the current player
 - C) The game ends immediately
 - D) The mark is overwritten
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How does the code check for a win in a column?

- A) By summing the ASCII values of the characters
 - B) By checking if all elements in a column are the same and not '-'
 - C) By checking if the column contains any '-'
 - D) It doesn't check columns, only rows
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After the main method executes, whose turn is it (value of currentPlayer)?

- A) X
 - B) O
 - C) -
 - D) Game Over
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Which variable holds the mutable state of the game board?

- A) currentPlayer
- B) row
- C) col
- D) board

End of Block: Large Code 2 Comprehension